

**IMPROVING URBAN AGRICULTURE USING VERTICAL FARMING
FOR THE COMMUNITY IN CASE OF WOLAITA SODO.**

**IMPROVING URBAN AGRICULTURE USING VERTICAL
FARMING FOR THE COMMUNITY IN CASE OF WOLAITA
SODO.**

A Thesis proposal Submitted In Partial Fulfillment of the requirement

For the Award of

B.Sc.

In

Architecture

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Declaration

The candidate, declare that this thesis is my own original work and it has not been presented for a degree in any other workers and all sources of material used for this thesis are duly acknowledged. This thesis is submitted to partial fulfillment of the requirement of B.Sc. degree at wolaita Sodo University, Department of Architecture.

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Dedication

I dedicate this thesis project to Almaz Tilahun who has given me the reason to do best thing in my life.

Abstract

Architecture and urban planning has proven to be an important element in shaping life styles, solving problems and giving new ways of living in the urban arena. The quality of urban life is

one of the big goals that the field tries to reach. Urban agriculture areas; vertical farming activities are known to enhance the quality of urban life. So, every city needs these urban agriculture. The planning and design of urban agriculture have been practiced in different parts of the world in different ways. The practice and use of these agricultural practice differed from place to place as well as from time to time. A good approach in the planning and designing of urban agriculture; vertical farming is to first study the past and current trends of urban agricultural practices in a place. The existing local culture acts as a guiding element to design urban agriculture suitable for the need of urban households; apartment residents. The target objectives of the study will be improving the concept of vertical farming architecture to the urban community, by connecting urban agriculture; vertical farming with apartments; urban households and promote a Place making with alternative methods of food production and ... ns that faced on the city.

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Chapter

1

IMPROVING URBAN AGRICULTURE USING VERTICAL FARMING FOR THE COMMUNITY IN CASE OF WOLAITA SODO.

1.1 Introduction

Urban agriculture is the way growing of plants and the raising of animals within and around cities. urban agriculture categorized to horizontal farming and vertical farming; horizontal urban farming is one kind of urban agriculture and it is the process of growing foods and works in animal production horizontally and Vertical Farming is the process of growing crops vertically, which is the combination of skyscraper or greenhouse effect together to form the advanced level of agriculture practices; this vertical farming technology is used to cultivate crops through the artificial sunlight or through the direct sunlight process.

The term urban agriculture or vertical farming is a bridge that connects architecture and agriculture; and architects are key solutions for social, economic and environmental problems of urban areas. So the researcher observes many problems in his life time and listed as a problem

statement and different questions are raised when the researcher observe the problems; those questions are research questions. The researcher has objective and scope based on problem statement and research questions.

The researcher do context analysis by using different data; secondary and primary data collection methods and interpreting these data within data interpretation system. Based on different findings the researcher recommended and concluded by bountiful appropriate solutions for the problems and major findings on case area analysis.

1.2 Background

With a population of more than 100 Million, and per capita GDP of less than 392 USD, Ethiopia is one of the poorest countries in the world (World Bank 2010). Agriculture is a key sector for the economy with 41% of GDP contribution. Therefore, in the past two decades, the government of Ethiopia has given huge emphasis in implementing the agricultural development and poverty reduction strategies. Because of these efforts the government Ethiopia has registered impressive economic growth in the past decade. However, the growth registered mostly has been dependent on the agricultural sector which is the center of the economy. But growth of the agricultural sector has not been increasing unabated in the recent past. As to the government of Ethiopia, focusing on urban re-development and resettling, and with the current land tenure policy, there seems to be less attention given to expand and support the urban Agriculture practices; and yet, little has been researched to justify the socio-economic relevance of urban agriculture in cities.

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Some observational and qualitative evidences show that urban agricultural practices are present in Ethiopian major parts of the cities especially in pri-urban of the cities. Though there is less interest to support urban agricultural practices in medium scale mainly at city centers, the government still supports and promotes urban farming in the pri-urban of the cities to reduce unemployment and improve livelihood of the urban farming households. This study was motivated by a huge expansion urban agriculture, especially vertical farming in Ethiopia; particularly in wolaita sodo there is a promotion and support by government and nongovernmental organization and there is a need to give know how about vertical farming, promotion and support to it.

During the research there were around 8177 urban households participating urban agriculture in Addis Ababa (Addis Ababa trade and industry development bureau, survey 2012/13, unpublished) and a lot of urban households were practicing in wolaita sodo; by using this concept as a base for vertical farming and improving it to be successful on this sector.

1.3 Problem statement

currently the number of populations increasing dramatically related to this different problem are happening like the shortage of fresh foods like fruit and vegetables and the existence of different diseases due to lack of this fresh food. The Cause of these population growth is due to the migration of maximum number of populations from rural areas to urban because of job opportunities, lack of arable lands and agricultural product decrease.

In other way there were also different environmental, social and economic problems like:-Loss of biodiversity and green space due to deforestation for getting new cultivation and farming area, Decreasing area of arable lands since such lands loss their fertility due to repetitive farming and by the side effect of artificial fertilizer/ The absence of organic waste recycling/, Dwindling of natural resources and biodiversity for farming and cultivation land due to the rise of the population, Deforestation of large amount of land but if we apply vertical farming Take up a considerably smaller footprint than conventional farms both reducing the need to deforesting large amounts of land, while also allowing existing farms to return to their natural state (promoting the absorption of more carbon dioxide). Absence of knowledge about alternative urban agriculture techniques and methods, Lack of knowledge about urban agriculture due to absence of education about it and post-harvest cost is the other problem to urban community.

Based on the above general clarification on the problems now the researcher going to explain different problems in the case of wolaita sodo like the requirement of large area to cultivate plants in a conventional farming, Small yield gotten in a conventional farming, Problem of water since the amount of water required in a conventional farm is high due to evaporation, a problem of outbreak of disease and insects on conventional farming and this leads to loss of crop or plant yields, bad weather makes farming difficult, risky and Floods.

The structural map of the city grouped urban agriculture zone on the outside of the city/ suburb zones of the city; these separates urban residence and condominiums to urban agriculture; vertical farming. The agricultural practices in the city doesn't provide additional services for the community and it haven't much functional with sustainability aspects of urban agriculture; vertical farming to urban community.

1.4 Research questions

1. How vertical farming architecture promotes communal and recreational space can be a means of gaining fresh food and it can be a means of creating job opportunity?

2. Why vertical farming architecture considered as a basic infrastructure; integrated with condominium households?
3. What role architects play on sustainability issues by applying vertical farming architecture and are the promotion of sustainability as a set of values?

1.5 Objectives of the study

1.5.1 General objective

The target objectives of the study will be improving the concept of vertical farming architecture to the urban community; condominium households, and promote a Place making with alternative methods of food production and practicing it to solve agricultural and other related problems that faced on the city.

1.5.2 Specific objective

- To improve the concept of vertical farming as a means of gaining fresh foods to urban areas.
- To create backyard space for condominium households.
- To show that the experience of architects on vertical farming as a means of social, environmental and economic sustainability.
- To show that vertical farming is one aspect of creating job opportunity.
- To promote that vertical farming can be used as a communal space and recreational area: - a place of meeting and coming together.
- To treat this problem as a problem of infrastructure. The vertical farm has the power to become an important and even essential component of the various systems (energy, water, waste) that help run this city and all others.
- To create market garden sense on residential and apartment building.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The main function of the study will be the discovery of the new ideas vertical farming architecture to the community and the community practicing this study on the practical world zone and addressing these to study project urban areas of the country.

In line with the problems indicated above on the problem statement, studying the environmental, social and economic contribution of urban agriculture especially vertical farming to urban farmers and urban households at large would be timely and necessary. The output of the research would improve our knowledge about the role urban agriculture plays in improving the welfare/ livelihood of the urban people; have a great significance for the target groups to be successful

with the objective of the study. The study will add information to the limited research done so far on the role and impact of urban agriculture in the Ethiopia.

Data generated may help architects, researchers, policy makers and extension workers in policy design, development of improved technologies and enable the public to recognize the sector's role

In the city's economic development and provide priorities to the sector. The study will bring new insight into the most debatable role of urban agriculture (i.e. its impact on household welfare, like food security and income). This will help researchers and NGOs to further analyze their intervention based on what works and what does not work in the urban settings.

It have also a great significance on sustainability issues: - social, environmental and economic sustainability for our country.

1.7 Scope of the study

1.7.1 Thematic scope

The scope of the study will be from the idea of the discovering urban agriculture and practicing it to solve problems facing to the urban areas in related to fresh food addressing problems and other related problems that I explained on the problem statement step, up to fulfilling sustainability issue.

1.7.2 Spatial scope

On the city of wolaita sodo and around it.

1.8 Limitation of the Study

One of the limitations to this study was the absence of counterfactual data on the control group. An artificial control group has created using statistical techniques like PSM. This is to reduce the problem of self-selection through using instrumental variables, retired and households who own house. Apart from this, the study had adopted robust econometric techniques to control unobservable and observable differences between participants and non-participants

1.10 Organization of the Report

Chapter one discuss the introduction part, including the background of the study, statement of the problem, the significance, scope and objectives of the study. Chapter two presents the Review of Literature while chapter three discuss the Research Methodology applied. Chapter

four presents the finding of the study and discussion; while chapter five discuss the conclusion and policy suggestion hared the study findings.

Chapter two

2. Literature review

Detail Definition, farming architecture science and vertical farming apartment concepts

2.1 What is urban agriculture?

Urban agriculture can be defined shortly as the growing of plants and the raising of animals within and around cities.

The most striking feature of urban agriculture, which distinguishes it from rural agriculture, is that it is integrated into the urban economic and ecological system: urban agriculture is embedded in -and interacting with- the urban ecosystem.

Such linkages include the use of urban residents as labourers, use of typical urban resources (like organic waste as compost and urban wastewater for irrigation), direct links with urban consumers, direct impacts on urban ecology (positive and negative), being part of the urban food system, competing for land with other urban functions, being influenced by urban policies and plans, etc.

Figure 2.1 urban agriculture activities

Urban agriculture is not a relic of the past that will fade away (urban agriculture increases when the city grows) nor brought to the city by rural immigrants that will lose their rural habits over time. It is an integral part of the urban system.

Urban Agriculture promotes community development and education, and increases self-reliance, community health, wildlife habitat, environmental awareness and social interaction among residents. It plays a crucial role in achieving food sovereignty and strengthening the local food network of a city.

2.2 In each city a further specification of urban agriculture is possible by looking at the following dimensions:

Types of actors involved. Large part of the people involved in urban agriculture is the urban poor.

Types of location. Urban agriculture may take place in locations inside the cities (intra-urban) or in the peri-urban areas.

The activities may take place on the homestead (on-plot) or on land away from the residence (off-plot), on private land (owned, leased) or on public land (parks, conservation areas, along roads, streams and railways), or semi-public land (schoolyards, grounds of schools and hospitals).

Types of products grown. Urban agriculture includes food products, from different types of crops (grains, root crops, vegetables, mushrooms, fruits) and animals (poultry, rabbits, goats, sheep, cattle, pigs, guinea pigs, fish, etc.) as well as non-food products (like aromatic and medicinal herbs, ornamental plants, tree products, etc.) or combinations of these.

2.3 Why urban agriculture?

The rapid urbanization that is taking place goes together with a rapid increase in urban poverty and urban food insecurity.

By 2020 the developing countries of Africa, Asia, and Latin America will be home to some 75% of all urban dwellers, and to eight of the anticipated nine mega-cities with populations in excess of 20 million.

It is expected that by 2020, about 40-45% of the poor in Africa and Asia will be concentrated in towns and cities.

Most cities in developing countries have great difficulties to cope with this development and are unable to create sufficient formal employment opportunities for the poor.

They also have increasing problems with the disposal of urban wastes and waste water and maintaining air and river water quality.

Urban agriculture provides a complementary strategy to reduce urban poverty and food insecurity and enhance urban environmental management.

The importance of urban agriculture is increasingly being recognised by international organisations like UN-Habitat and FAO (World Food and Agriculture Organisation).

Types of urban agriculture and garden agriculture

Institutional Farms and Gardens; Affiliated with an institution (such as hospitals, churches, prisons, schools, public housing) whose primary mission is not food production, but which have goals that urban agriculture supports.

Community Gardens; Most of these gardens provide space for several different activities, including growing vegetables and flowers, as well as providing gathering space for socializing.

Community Farm; Tend to be communal growing spaces operated by a non-profit organization that engages the surrounding community in food production but also social and educational programming.

Commercial Farm; In general, commercial farmers try to maximize crop performance in order to achieve profitability, however, some share many of the health and ecological goals of the broader urban agriculture community.

Poly House a Poly House is a tunnel made of polyethylene, usually semi-circular, square or elongated in shape. The interior heats up because incoming solar radiation from the sun warms plants, soil, and other things inside the building faster than heat can escape the structure.

2.4 What is Vertical Farming?

Prime agricultural land can be scarce and expensive. With worldwide population growth, the demand for both more food and more land to grow food is ever increasing. But some entrepreneurs and farmers are beginning to look up, not out, for space to grow more food.

One solution to our need for more space might be found in the abandoned warehouses in our cities, new buildings built on environmentally damaged lands, and even in used shipping

containers from ocean transports. This solution, called vertical farming, involves growing crops in controlled

Although small, residential vertical gardening (including window farms) has been around for decades, commercial-scale vertical farms have only been seriously examined in the United States for the past few years. As of early 2015, the United States had only a handful of commercial vertical farms under operation. But the interest in this new farming technology is growing rapidly, and entrepreneurs in several American cities are taking a serious look at this innovative farming system.

Vertical Farming is the process, which is the combination of skyscraper or greenhouse effect together to form the advanced level of agriculture practices; this vertical farming technology is used to cultivate crops through the artificial sunlight or through may be the direct sunlight process. Greenhouse effect is the harmful to the earth environment so this system minimize the greenhouse effect partially and it is composed by the natural manner, most of the vertical farming are not build with the eco-friendly appearance. But this vertical farming has the less made of glass which can pass the oxygen to the outer layer of the farming areas

The vertical farming requires the water harvesting, hydroponics technique, fade type of glasses and suitable architecture structure to the vertical farming in the way of designing potentially.

2.5 FARMING ARCHITECTURE/ farm and buildings/:

It is the real topic to sow the role of architects in solving agricultural infrastructure to give service on other building types like hotel agriculture, apartment agriculture, mixed use agriculture, and other. The vertical farming architecture is categorized into various sections that there are energy management, water management it also known as hydroponics, cropping method and harvesting manner etc. The vertical farming architecture is also depended on the construction oriented process, where it takes the complex situation some times that there enough sunlight radiation has to pass on all crops of the plants for the healthy growth.

Renewable Resources:

Vertical Farming system is designed for the future purposes where the sources such as electricity, low level of water availability are may or may not be occurred in the future days. So in the way of handling those situations the system involved with the renewable resourcing process, where the wind mill can be used to generate electricity for the water pump process for supplying water to the crops, and solar energy are also added additionally to generate power for the producing of artificial sunlight to the crops.

Reaping Process:

The reaping process also known as water management process, thus especially the water is going to be managed in the vertical farming structure. Where some of the methods are going to be discussed such as rain water harvesting method, this method explains that water which are collected for the rain are too passed through pipes to crops, so by getting of the rain water through indirect process will get an healthy and natural yielding, these activities are done through the hydroponic system it is stated as the nutrient content are going to be passed on the crops through the pipes, while flowing of water to the crops regularly the mineral is also to be added in the water.

Vertical farming apartment

Figure 2-2. mixed residential and agricultural tower apartment

“We live vertically within apartments and luxury residence’s why we don’t farm vertically integrated within our buildings?”P. Platt, “Vertical Farming: An Interview with Dickson Despommier,” *Gastronomica*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 80–87, 2007.).

In our cities of the country peoples live vertically with in vertical elements of the city like apartments, residences, condominiums and other residential units but they didn’t Farm vertically by integrating the farming structure to their apartments and residential units due to various reasons. Based on this consideration to farm it is necessary to know about urban agriculture: - vertical farming; garden architecture and vertical farming apartment or mixed residential and agricultural units. Urban agriculture can be defined shortly as the growing of plants and the raising of animals within and around cities and Vertical Farming is the process of growing crops

vertically, which is the combination of skyscraper or greenhouse effect together to form the advanced level of agriculture practices; this vertical farming technology is used to cultivate crops through the artificial sunlight or through the direct sunlight process. There is also vertical farming apartments that connects the residential units with agricultural units under the technology of vertical farming and residential units and it is also combination of green apartment with agricultural units on each layers of the building with in different methods of farming architecture like roof garden farming, terrace farming and balcony farming of the apartment building or any other residential buildings. (SSRG International Journal of Agriculture & Environmental Science (SSRG-IJAES) – volume 1 Issue 1 October 2014)

Figure 1.3 Vertical farming apartment/Mixed use agricultural/residential tower with PV skin, wind turbines, irrigation.

Why vertical farming apartments around the world; Ethiopia

- Ever increasing population particularly in urban centres (According to the United Nations Population Division (2009), the world population will increase from about 6.9 billion in 2010 to 9.2 billion in 2050 or an addition of about 2.3 billion more people to feed is directly proportional with the housing needs of the population.
- the percentage of urban population will likewise increase from 50.46% in 2010 to 68.70% in 2050. It is expected that world population will continue to increase.
- currently, the rate of growth per year is about 80 million (80 million people are added to the world’s population every year) this indicates there is also 80 million housing need and food need. □ Almost all of this netpopulationincrease-97%- is in developing country.

- According to, unofficial data Ethiopia population close to 100 million this data shows population density, housing and food are direct proportional.
- Ethiopia urban centres are receiving high influx of population due to rural – urban Migration

- on the other hand there is continues shrinking of land.
- to this end, food and nutrition insecurity, and poverty are major phenomenon in urban Centres which particularly affects the urban poor and unemployed youth
- So, urban farming is the best alternative to feed the ever increasing urban population
- However, space shortage particularly in congested urban corners restrained urban Farming.
- Congested urban corners mainly occupied by the most poor and destitute population
- in this connection, practicing vertical farming is the paramount solution to improve the livelihood situation of the poor and destitute population group
- Very much in line with the Ethiopian urban poverty reduction policy and strategy

Advantage of vertical farming apartment

- Land maximization: vertical farming maximizes the limited ground spaces which increase the land size so many times. Of course the size of the ground space increment determined by the number of vegetable growing beds constructed above the ground
- Environmental benefits: this technology is using disposable plastic bottles to grow vegetables which otherwise would be thrown in to anywhere and spoil and pollute the environment, this in turn contribute to reduce environmental pollution
- beautifies the city and increase urban green space and improves urban physical environment
- Increase production: vertical farm used to increase volume of production per unit area of land
- Economic benefits
- Generate in-kind income: urban farmers consume variety of foods from own produces which in turn increase food availability at households level
- Generate cash income: create money by turning the surplus produces into cash

- Create job opportunity: vertical farming can be the best job creation opportunity for urban unemployed youth and provides employment for people with limited skills and formal education
- Year-round Production: vertical farming technology can ensure vegetable production all year-round (4 rounds and above/year)
- Water Conservation: the vertical farming technology uses a combination of drip and hydroponics irrigation system which uses 50 percent lesser water than normal gardening and can retain water
- recycling: urban degradable solid wastes will be used for making compost
- Organic vegetable production: The controlled growing conditions will allow a reduction or total abandonment of the use of chemical pesticides, fertilizers, etc.
- Health benefits
 - Vegetable production conducted in Ethiopia in general and Addis Ababa in particular following much polluted rivers which has Health hazards both for producers and consumers. So, vertical farming can mitigate this problem
 - Urban farming contributes for outdoor exercise that helps aged people to counteract their physical passivity, while doing routine activities like watering, etc.
- Manageability: producing vegetables through vertical farm is easily manageable, and producers don't have much contact with soil and plant while during management
- can be practice in every corner of the city including congested urban areas, even on top of buildings, on the wall of buildings, etc. since it needs small space only to fix the Vertical farm where vegetables grow
- We can produce vegetables even in concert grounds with layers of vertically stacked grow-beds
- Not labour intensive: can be run by family labour even by a single person
- can be practiced by aged people, disabled, women, men, youth, etc. since it needs less labour
- Marketability: since vegetables produced on vertical farming are clean and safe and can be preferable for consumption which in turn attract market and generate more Profit

- **Affordability:** vertical farm is constructed from locally available materials such as wooden poles, disposable plastic bottles, etc. it request relatively considerable installation cost, however it can be run by minimum cost for the following 3-4 years even more
- **Sustainable Urban Growth:** vertical farming, applied in a holistic approach in conjunction with other technologies, can allow urban areas to absorb the expected influx of more population and yet still remain food sufficient. The technology could provide more employment to the rural populace expected to converge to the cities in the years to come

Why inspire the innovator to focus on vertical farming

- He likes vegetable very much, however vegetables that are produced in Addis are not clean and safe because it has been produced following chronically polluted rivers
- this situation forced him to seek solutions so as to get fresh, clean and organic vegetables
- So, he realize vertical farming is the best solution to mitigate the problem
- Again, he thought the technology has not only helping to get

Aspects of urban agriculture in Ethiopia

Food security: In Ethiopia, urban agriculture has been shown to be a final stage by households in their sequence of survival strategies. Households in the urban areas respond to the extreme threat of poverty and food insecurity by carrying out urban farming on any vacant space available. Urban agriculture is also practised because of shortage of income and unemployment in the urban centres.

Nutritional aspect: Urban agriculture has also been studied as a contributor to improved nutritional levels among the urban poor in Ethiopia. Vegetable production has been very important in most of the studies. Most of the urban population in Ethiopia consists of the poor who cannot afford to buy high-valued food stuffs.

Access to land: In Ethiopia, urban agriculture is carried out on land in transitional use where usufruct rights are at issue. This problem leads to low investment in urban agriculture and hence poor productivity.

2.5.1 ASSETS OF VERTICAL FARMING THAT RELATE WITH APARTMENTS:

There are many assets are in the vertical farming technology where one of the most benefit is reliable cropping, there is no any seasonal cropping is not needed as the every process of the system are done with the interior process so the crops can harvest at any season in interior farming, by applying of this technique there will be no crop loss occurred and also other benefit of interior framing are stated as

No bugs can infect crops and climatic changes are also not affect the crops. Energy is less utilized in the vertical farming system where led lights are used instead of the sunlight for the growing of crops better than under the sunlight.

Also this system reduces the labour cost where like the agriculture field work only more number of labours and our system requires only less manpower. As the less amount water is enough for the vertical farming technology. While if the land based agriculture it requires more of water in order cover all the crops of the land, but the vertical farming a separate faucet is linked individually to every crops of the system.

ECOFRIENDLY METHODOLOGY:

As the vertical farming system has the various methodologies it is the eco-friendly process, as we can able to cultivate any kind of crops at any duration process, multiple-crops can be cultivated in this process and if the heavy rain came it can be able to damage all crops of the system but in this system the crops are protected under the buildings so the plant or crops cannot be affected through rain. The water used in this system which can be used again by the recycling process is stated as the water are passed over hydroponics system and the excess amount of water is collected and made into the recycling process. It's a fully eco-friendly technique where new kind of crops can also be developed easily in the vertical farming system. And the plants or crops which are grown under vertical farming are free from pesticides and it makes the healthy food when it is compared

to the land farming system. This kind of technique is fully get successful on the urban areas to move the green environment.

Waste Reduction:

The waste reduction is the one of the benefit of the vertical farming technique where in case of land farming the crops or plants get damaged due to heavy rain and pesticides, where in case of the vertical farming the waste is reduced by the interior agriculture methods, and energy for the vertical farming are usually managed with the solar and wind power so that the energy utilized

are renewable sources and vehicular transportation also the important phase of the vertical farming apartment where transportation costs are reduced.

Increased Growing Area:

Now a day's there is increment of vertical farming and green houses are developed where it is fully build with the hydroponic and renewable resource based, which completely created with the advanced management, where greenhouse are not fit for the earth environment but the combined of vertical farming and green house where carbon dioxide are passed over the outer location of the building. By applying of vertical farming there will be the maximum crop yielding, make the temperature controlled manner.

INTEGRATED TECHNOLOGY:

The integrated technology is one of the most advancement in the vertical farming technique where the system has to be completely controlled with the computers and other embedded systems such as sensors etc., but in our system the integrated system which has to be to analyse water, air and mineral maintenance. While if take the air quality management the crops and plants are needed the Carbon dioxide and this supplied by the air management integration system, as plants has to develop in the health manner a separated separate system has to be created as well as the water and air quality also managed.

2.6 CLASIFICATION OF VERTICAL FARMING

Vertical farming Apartment systems can be further classified by the type of structure that building the system.

Apartment Building-based vertical farms are often housed in abandoned apartment buildings in residential zones of the cities.

Shipping-container vertical farms are an increasingly popular option. These vertical farms use 40-foot shipping containers, normally in service carrying goods around the world. Shipping containers are being refurbished by several companies into self-contained vertical farms, complete with LED lights, drip-irrigation systems, and vertically stacked shelves for starting and growing a variety of plants.

Figure 2-4 interior part of Chicago's the plant vertical farm apartment and freight farm shipping container vertical farming.

Figure 2-5: exterior part of Chicago's the plant vertical farm apartment and freight farm shipping container vertical farming.

2.6.1 What Are the Pros and Cons of Vertical Farming apartments?

Continuous Crop Production:

Vertical farming apartment technology can ensure crop production year-round in non-tropical regions. And the production is much more efficient than land-based farming. According to Despommier, a single indoor

Elimination of Herbicides and Pesticides:

The controlled growing conditions in a vertical farm allow a reduction or total abandonment of the use of chemical pesticides. Some vertical farming operations use ladybugs and other biological controls when needed to deal with any infestations.

Protection from Weather-Related Variations in Crop Production:

Because crops in a vertical farm are grown under a controlled environment, they are safe from extreme weather occurrences such as droughts, hail, and floods.

Water Conservation and Recycling:

Hydroponic growing techniques used in vertical farms use about 70% less water than normal agriculture (and aeroponic techniques, which involve the misting of plant roots, use even less water).

Climate Friendly:

Growing crops indoors reduces or eliminates the use of tractors and other large farm equipment commonly used on outdoor farms, thus reducing the burning of fossil fuel. According to Despommier, deploying vertical farms on a large scale could result in a significant reduction in air pollution and in CO2 emissions.

People Friendly:

Conventional farming is one of the most hazardous occupations in the United States. Some common occupational hazards that are avoided in vertical farming are accidents in operating large and dangerous farming equipment and exposure to poisonous chemicals.

Land and Building Costs:

Urban locations for vertical farms can be quite expensive. Some existing vertical farms are based in abandoned warehouses, derelict areas, or Superfund sites, which can be more economical for construction.

Energy Use:

Although transportation costs may be significantly less than in conventional agriculture, the energy consumption for artificial lighting and climate control in a vertical farm can add significantly to operations costs.

Controversy over USDA Organic Certification:

It is unclear if or when there will be agreement on whether crops produced in a vertical farm can be certified organic. Many agricultural specialists feel that a certified organic crop involves an

entire soil ecosystem and natural system, not just the lack of pesticides and herbicides.

Limited Number of Crop Species:

The current model for crops grown in vertical farms focuses on high-value, rapid-growing, small-footprint, and quick-turnover crops, such as lettuce, basil, and other salad items. Slower-growing vegetables, as well as grains, aren't as profitable in a commercial vertical farming system.

Pollination Needs:

Crops requiring insect pollination are at a disadvantage in a vertical farm, since insects are usually excluded from the growing environment. Plants requiring pollination may need to be pollinated by hand, requiring staff time and labour.

Vertical farming apartments may be constructed integrated with different

Types of Vertical Farms

Vertical farms come in different shapes and sizes, from simple two-level or wall-mounted systems to large warehouses several stories tall. But all vertical farms use one of three soil-free systems for providing nutrients to plants: - hydroponic, aeroponic, or aquaponic. The following information describes these three growing systems:

Figure 2-5: hydroponics vertical farming system

Aeroponics: The National Aeronautical and Space Administration (NASA) is responsible for developing this innovative indoor growing technique. In the 1990s, NASA was interested in finding efficient ways to grow plants in space and coined the term “aeroponics,” defined as “growing plants in an air/mist environment with no soil and very little water.”

Figure 2-6: aeroponic vertical farming system

Aquaponics. An aquaponic system takes the hydroponic system one step further, combining plants and fish in the same ecosystem. Fish are grown in indoor ponds, producing nutrient-rich waste that is used as a feed source for the plants in the vertical farm. The plants, in turn, filter and purify the wastewater, which is recycled to the fish ponds. Although aquaponics is used in smaller-scale vertical farming systems, most commercial vertical farm systems focus on producing only a few fast-growing vegetable crops and don't include an aquaponics component.

This simplifies the economics and production issues and maximizes efficiency. However, new standardized aquaponic systems may help make this closed-cycle system more popular.

Figure2-7: aquaponic vertical farming system

AQUAPONICS

Aquaponics is cultivation of fish and plants together in a constructed, recirculating ecosystem. Aquaponics utilizes natural bacterial cycles to turn fish waste into plant nutrients. A large amount of plant material can be produced in a small space. Aquaponics combines aquaculture and hydroponics. Aquaponics systems have three main elements: Fish, plants and bacteria. The farmer feeds the fish.

Aquaculture

“Aquaculture is a form of agriculture encompassing the propagation, cultivation and marketing of aquaponic animals and plants, including fish for food such as catfish, tilapia and trout, ornamental fish such as koi and aquaria, bait fish for the fishing industry, sport fish for restocking ponds and lakes and fish for feed ingredients.” (Nelson & Pade 2008, 21.).

2.6.4 DESIGNING AN AQUAPONICS SYSTEM

There are many things to consider when you are planning an aquaponics system. There isn't one and correct way to build an aquaponics system. In following chapters we open up what are the main types of aquaponics systems. Nutrient film technique, raft or media bed? The choice depends on the goal, if the system is going to be a small backyard system or big commercial system and materials that are available. While the nutrient film technique and raft systems are good for commercial systems. For especially herbs and lettuce a media bed system can support bigger plants and is the cheapest one to build. After that we'll find out something about the plumbing, siphons and pumps.

Nutrient Film Technique

The Nutrient Film Technique (Figure 3.) Is a common method in hydroponic production? Plants are grown in channels where nutrient solution is pumped through. Ideally, the bottoms of the roots are exposed to the nutrient solution while the tops of the roots are kept moist but not waterlogged.

Figure 2-8: NFT plants grow in special pipes

Raft

A raft system (Figure 4.) uses floating beds for plants. All water in the system is recirculated constantly from the fish tank through filters and large water-filled shallow tanks. The raft system is commercially viable. The large volume of water provides a buffer, and in a commercial system it's easy to move rafts around according to the age of the crops. There is also lots of base data available. It does however require daily and periodic filter cleaning, and utilises lots of components. (Nelson & Pade 2008, 48-53)

Media bed

Figure 2-9: raft

The word “media” describes the “substrate” that’s placed inside the grow bed. In biology substrate is defined as “...a natural environment in which an organism lives, or the surface or medium on which an organism grows or is attached.” (Aquaponicsworld n.d.)

Siphons and plumbing

Research has shown that the flooding, and then rapid draining of the grow beds, provides for excellent access to nutrients for the plants, and high oxygenation for the plant roots. The rapid draining draws oxygen down fully into the roots and this is vital for good growth. At its simplest, the siphon is a mechanism for moving water from one reservoir to another, lower reservoir. The benefit of the siphon is that it is capable of raising water over a barrier – and this makes it distinctive, and a practical benefit to aquaponics.

Pumps

When you are planning your system, you need to think if you will be running a one pump or a two pump system. In a one pump system you raise the water from the lowest point of your system to the highest, and let the rest of the water flow back via gravity. A one pump system uses less power than a two pump system, and if one of the pumps fails it doesn’t pump the whole system empty....The two pump system however doesn’t require as much height difference between the highest and lowest points.

Inputs in an aquaponic system

An aquaponics system provides possibility to grow fish and plants in a closed cycle. Following chapters will give an idea about what type of crops can be grown in an aquaponics system, fish species and what can be fed for the fish. Choosing right species of fish to fit your climate can save trouble later on. Many things can be grown in aquaponics system, anything from herbs, leafy greens and vegetables to even small fruit trees. The type of fish depends on personal preference, market price and climate. Be sure to choose species that suit your location as introducing invasive species to new areas isn't a good idea.

2.6.5 Common fish species for aquaponics gardening

As you can't grow plants without nutrients, you need fish. Once you add fish to a tank you will see the ammonia level begins to rise. After 7-10 days, the ammonia level will begin to fall and nitrite level begins to rise. In another 7-10 days, nitrite levels will begin to fall and nitrate level will begin to rise. This happens by natural microbial processes. Ideally, you should only stock your fish tank by less than 20% of the total biomass that your system can support, by means of fish weight. This reduces fish mortality and allows the bacteria population to get established. It also leaves room for fish to grow and gives the possibility for adding some more later. (Nelson & Pade 2008, 105.)

Fish feed

You can feed your fish at least once a day, but can also feed them more often for faster growth or additional nutrients for plant beds if required. Commercial aquaculture operations can feed their fish as often as once an hour. You need to be careful not to overfeed the fish. The best rule of thumb is to feed your fish only what they will eat within five minutes. After five minutes, remove remaining food from the tank. Automatic feeders are ok, but if your fish decide not to eat you won't notice that there could be something wrong with your system. Fish may stop eating for various reasons. Reasons might be change in water temperature, pH being outside tolerable range, too much ammonia and/or nitrites, not enough oxygen, stress or disease. Problems can be fixed if they are caught early (Bernstein 2011, 147-151.)

2.7 Urban agriculture concepts in Ethiopia:-Ethiopia has registered a growth rate of 11% with significant improvements in various sectors including service, agriculture and even the industry (MoFED F. report 2010/11). With a fast growing population, a decrease in land holding size per household, increase of unemployment, persistent food insecurity as well as environmental and social challenges, it will be a huge challenge to the government to maintain the growth rate and achieve its ambitious Growth and Transformation Plan (GTP). This GTP plan assumes of making Ethiopia a middle income country by 2025. Among the top priorities of

the GTP plan to ensure food security through building a strong agricultural sector is the one; which is not only expected to feed the nation, but also support the growth of the industry. According to Yonas Alem (2011), the growth of the Ethiopian economy brought huge inflation in food and non-food goods, particularly in food commodities. The government had also taken some measures in 2008 by lifting certain taxes from food commodities (especially oil), as well as measures to curb the excess supply of money. These fiscal and monetary measures might take time to reduce prices and lead to improved food security of the urban dwellers especially the poor. This had a very negative welfare impact on the urban than rural households; while the rural households are supported by various safety net programs. Combined with huge unemployment, high cost of living, growing population, urban people have developed various mechanisms to cope with the changes. One of the coping mechanisms adopted by the urban dwellers has been to engage with urban farming. Various studies such as RUFA (2007), FAO (2002), and UN-Habitat (2013) have documented the contributions of urban agriculture to the socio-economic wellbeing of the producers, the community as well as to the ecosystem of the urban areas. However, the findings of such studies are still debatable and their applications defer from country to country. For example, in one province in Nigeria, households were able to generate around 74% of their agricultural income through urban farming (Salau and Attah 2012). Most of the urban populations in Ethiopia are dependent on rural farmers in fulfilling their basic food needs; while the poor, elderly and disadvantaged urban dwellers are engaged on urban agriculture to supplement their food demand; and generate their side line income (Tewodros, 2007).

Empirical Evidence

The high growth of urban areas and urban population is a worldwide phenomenon. According to the Ministry of Works and Urban Development, Ethiopia has a high rate of urbanization, averaging about 4.3% per annum (MoWUD, 2006). About 30% of this population is concentrated in the capital city, Addis-Ababa.

Conceptual Frame Work

On the following framework, it is tried to portray the general concepts of the study. Specifically, it indicates the direct or indirect relationship and/or effect of urban farming practice on specified impact indicator variables (level of household income and food security, measured by households' food expenditure).

Figure 2-10: conceptual flow

Potentials and Constraints of Urban Agriculture

Since urban agriculture is practiced mainly within boundaries of cities, it has unique features with distinct potentials and constraints. Long-term benefits of cities from urban agriculture imply the contributions of the sector to sustainability of cities (Nugent, 1999). Nugent 1999 reported that studying urban agriculture from three dimensions: social, economic and ecological, is helpful to realize the net benefit; hence, it's sustainable contribution to the selected cities.

Potentials of Urban Agriculture

Urban agriculture is mainly practiced in the outskirts and vacant spaces of the city, and along riversides and urban fringes where land is not suitable for building construction. As Bryld (2003) puts it “urban agriculture brings with it great potentials for enhancing the situation of the urban citizens, especially those with the lowest incomes who are dependent on the access to locally grown food”.

Food Security

Most of urban farming is practiced by the urban poor who consume most of the production and supply, the surplus to market (Bryld 2003, Mireri et al. 2006). The major expense for most of the urban poor is purchasing of food; thus, they will be left with nothing for health, education and other necessities. They also hardly consume varieties of food. Thus, it is not surprising that urban farming contributes to improving livelihoods for the urban poor. RUAFA's (2007) report emphasized the role of urban agriculture as ensuring food security and healthy nutrition. This

report further indicated that food production in the city is in many cases a response of the urban poor to inadequate, unreliable and irregular access to food, and the lack of purchasing power.

Economic Potential

Urban farming can also be a good source of income for the urban poor, if it is especially practiced as a formal sector. However, Bryld (2003) doubted whether it has a significant contribution to macro economies of cities although he stated that urban farming has an economic relevance because it is helping urban farmers, especially the poor, to use their non-farm income for other purposes instead of purchasing food (i.e., it improves the welfare of urban farming households).

RUAF (2007) reported that the poor households in developing countries spend 50 to 70% of their income to purchase foods; hence, the foundation appreciated the benefits of self-growing crops and/or participating in other forms of urban agriculture by the urban poor. The report also confirmed that “in Addis Ababa, above-normal profits are earned by even the smallest-scale backyard producers with very low capital” (RUAF 2007). This finding also agrees with RUAF’s report.

Social Advantage: - Actors in urban agriculture came from various groups of urban society. They can be the poor or the rich, women or men, natives or migrants, and so on. The participation of mostly women and other vulnerable households in the sector draws attention, and implies the role of the sector in poverty alleviation and integrating urban societies (RUAF 2007). Thomas P. Z Mpofu (2013) reported that “urban farming helps vulnerable groups to reduce their dependency

on other people and strengthens social integration of the farmers by organizing them into cooperatives and also providing them an opportunity to earn additional income”.

Environmental Advantages

In most cases, urban agriculture is practiced in marginal spaces in cities and outskirts where lands are not suitable for other use. It, therefore, creates beautiful scenarios and landscapes, and improves microclimate, and nutrient recycling (Bryld 2003). The study established that, due to the favorable climatic conditions of Addis-Ababa and other Ethiopian cities (Bahirdar, Jimma, Mekele, Adama etc.) areas used for urban agriculture were green throughout the year. This contributed towards the creation of a micro-climate in some parts of the cities, as well as improves the city’s aesthetic value. Ever greenness also helped to clean the air by reducing dust and protecting the soil from erosion. Some respondents in the study area added that urban agriculture had protected their areas from being used as sites for the unhygienic dumping of wastes.

Constraints of Urban Agriculture

Despite the advantages of urban agriculture mentioned above, it has some limitations worth noticing. In many Ethiopian cities, it is being practiced as an informal sector and has little support from regional and federal ruling body (Bryceson 2005, Bryld 2003). There are a number of challenges that were facing the urban farmers in different Ethiopian cities. These were classified into three broad categories, namely: institutional, financial and capacity related challenges; the finding will be discussed under result chapter.

a. Space for Cultivation and Livestock keeping

Agriculture requires land; but, the first institutional challenge was lack of land tenure rights (Thomas P. Z. Mpofu 2013). This was regarded by many urban farmers as mostly restrictive to the growth and development of urban agriculture in Ethiopia in general and in Addis Ababa in particular. The existing unclear legal set up caused a sense of insecurity among most farmers, thus negatively affecting their commitment to invest in the development of the land whose ownership was uncertain. As a result, farmers lived in constant fear of being evicted from “their” land due to lack of tenure security.

Lack of Access to Resources

According to Drescher *et al.* (1999), the most critical institutional constraints to urban agriculture include lack of access to farming land as well as to farming inputs such as seeds, fertilizer, pesticides, and implements. Urban food markets are often designed, to import food from rural areas, while the input producing businesses are also oriented towards serving rural agriculture. Thus, both the input and output market systems and infrastructure often favor rural agriculture (UNDP, 2010). This is largely because the market structures tend to be composed of large wholesalers who purchase directly from rural areas or from intermediary wholesale markets at the edge of the city. Thus, generally, smaller urban farming households do not yet fit well into these structures.

Extension Contact/Service

One of the critical challenges facing most urban farmers was their limited skills in modern agriculture. This was attributed to lack of training and/or technical support to help them improve their skills and knowledge, and increase their productivity. According to Thomas P. Z. Mpofu (2013), in Addis Ababa about 44% of the farmers did not get any kind of technical advice from the agricultural extension workers. On its part, the Addis-Ababa Urban Agriculture Department admitted that they did not have enough experts to provide the required and continuous support to the urban farmers.

2.8 Urban Agriculture in the context of achieving MDGs

Urban and peri-urban agriculture can directly and indirectly contribute in pursuing several of The MDGs. UPA’s main direct contribution (over half of its effort) is to Goal 1, which combines the reduction of poverty and the reduction of hunger. A significant proportion (about one-fifth)

is directed to Goal 7 concerning environmental sustainability. Smaller percentages of resources are directed to empowering women (Goal 3). There are important indirect effects on goals covering primary education (Goal 2), child mortality (Goal 4), maternal health (Goal 5), and combating diseases (Goal 6), generated primarily by work addressing reduction of hunger and malnutrition. Focusing on food security, nutrition and right to food in urban and peri-urban areas will help city-dwellers to attain a better livelihood.

It will allow municipalities to broaden their strategy towards achieving the Millennium Development Goals. Most of the poor developing countries are net food buyers. The recent price spikes are believed to have pushed over one hundred million more people into extreme poverty. According to UN Habitat, rapid urbanization has profoundly altered the distribution and face of poverty. As cities grow, so do the slum populations, for example more than 90% of urban growth in Kenya during 1990s was in slum areas. Slum dwellers, who presently account for 1 billion of

the world wide urban population, are more likely to die earlier, experience more hunger and diseases, attend less education and have fewer chances of employment. Countries should adopt urban development policies including urban and peri-urban agriculture that will upgrade employment and income generating opportunities for the urban poor. Even though the proportion of people in the world suffering from malnutrition and hunger has fallen since the early 1990, the number of people with insufficient access to food has risen. FAO's latest estimates show that even before the recent surge in food prices, worrisome long term trends towards increasing hunger were already apparent. FAO estimates that 848 million people suffered from chronic hunger worldwide in 2003-05, representing an increase of six million from the nearly 842 million in 1990-92, the World Food Summit baseline period, against which progress is measured. With the number of chronically hungry people in the world now higher than during the baseline period, the World Food Summit target of reducing that number by half by the year 2015 may be more difficult to achieve.

Figure 2-11: Number of undernourished people in the developing world (WFS target and Proportion of undernourished people in the developing world (MDG target)

Most of the increase in undernourishment from the WFS benchmark period (1990-92) to 2003-05 took place in sub-Saharan Africa where the absolute number (WFS indicator) of hungry people increased by 43 million, from 169 million to 212 million. However, nearly three-quarters of this increase took place in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, where the number of hungry people rose from 11 million in 1990-92 to 43 million people in 2003-05, fuelled by widespread and persistent conflict. (3 From FAO-ESSG September 2008).

Applying urban agriculture; vertical farming on residential and apartment buildings

DESIGN GUIDELINES: Residential/ apartment Pre construction Methods:

- Planter boxes or planter beds can be incorporated in design
- Inverted beams in the construction of roof slab can act as planter beds
- Planter boxes with depth of 45cm has to be provided (Minimum soil depth to be 30cm)
- The spaces for farming vegetables should get good sunlight (minimum of 6 hours)
- Watering can be provided through drip irrigation or through a system of grey water recycling.
- Proper drain has to be provided for the garden to allow to water sewage.

Residential/ apartment Post Construction Methods:

- Use of silpaulin sheets as damp proofing material
- Use of thermo coal box, rubber box, plastic cover, rice sack for planting the plants
- Use of eco san toilet to provide cost effective fertilizer
- Use of reed drum systems to economically clean grey water, that could be used for watering can be provided as an afterthought also.

2.9 case study

2.9.1 Local case study

Dejenie Adem Vertical Farming, Lebu, Nifas silk Lafto,

Addis Abeba , Ethiopia.

Figure2-12: Dejenie Adem vertical farming process **General introduction**

As the practice of vertical farming food in stacked layers vertically, vertically inclined surfaces integrated within other structures, depending on the system used for constructions and productions.

A number of advantages have been listed under vertical farming as compared to the conventional farming; based on this fact Dejenie Adem vertical farming company its advantage practically. From those advantages; it reduces price for food as it eliminates costs such as transportation, it minimizes post-harvest losses due to spoilage and infestation, increase using small area of land, reducing the need for new farm land due to population growth; these saving many natural resources, currently threatened by deforestation or pollution.

Dejenie Adem wants to spread the idea of vertical farming of his company on different parts of the city to increase vertical farming participants.

Description of the project

Vertical farming may not be new or an even a recent topic in relation to the concept of urban agriculture and sustainable food production. However in the context of Ethiopia, where cities are currently in continuous expansion due to the population growth dramatically; the need to look up wards be sides sideway is becoming more inevitable in the companies perspectives.

Dejenie Adem vertical farming company has started looking up; by considering the owner of the companies' good experience of harvesting fresh vegetables from their small vertical farm that he

built in front of his house as a pilot project previously. Then the company practicing it by scale up.

Site development / massing

When he looking the idea in his mind and try to practice the idea in the practical world; so he select the void site in front of his house. And he develop the site by considering;- sun direction, circulation, free from sewage line, and so on.

Space usage and articulation

The space that Dejenie Adem vertical farming uses in front of his house is planned for the purpose of farming vertically in grid arrangement of bamboo shelves.

- The farming area used the empty space and free from any kind of utility lines
- The water line for farming activity is used free space in front of the farming area

Functional arrangement and flow

The arrangement and flow of the bamboo shelf for the farming purpose were arranged with a grid structure with different functional flow.

- Circulation space
- The area of bamboo shelf structure for growing purpose
- Water tank and space for drip irrigation system
- Compost area

Materials

Bamboos and Use & Throw Cups

Bamboos are the main parts of Dejene's vertical farm structure. They are vertically stacked in proportional heights and they have a number of holes with similar distances. This is where the use & throw plastic cups come to play. Filled with composted soil and kept in each holes of the vertically stacked bamboos, the cups are used (and no more thrown) to grow the vegetables.

The bamboo structured vertical farm has its own drip irrigation system to water the vegetables with a ten thousand liters tanker as a backup. Dejene produces vegetable seeds in his house and

composting takes place on the spot. Using this bamboo structure, which stands on 18 square meters of land, he grows variety of vegetables such as salad (China, German, freeze), broccoli, root beet, pepper, parsley, mint, and even legumes plants. He said the structure holds over 60 vegetable plants just in one square meter.

Technology

The technology that the vertical farming use is drip irrigation system for water distribution on the bamboo shelf for the vertical farming system.

Natural lighting, Structural solutions

The use of the bamboo structure shelf is to solve the shortage of natural light distribution to the growing bed. And the design use fully natural light.

This is one kind of structural solution for the problem of insufficient lighting problem.

2.9.2 External case study

CASE STUDY

Chitra & Vishwanath Residence, Bangalore

LOCATION: VIDYARANYAPURA, BANGALORE

CONSTRUCTED ON: 1995

DESIGN TEAM: CHITRA VISHWANATH (BIOME ENVIRONMENTAL SOLUTIONS PVT.

LTD.)

SITE: 30 FT X 50 FT

BUILT-UP AREA: 1,500

SQF

Drainage Pattern An "eco san" toilet placed on top of the roof provides nutrients to grow rice in a rooftop paddy patch which is irrigated using waste water from the washing machine which is treated using a three stage reed drum system.

Figure 2-13 external case study agricultural residence

Technical aspect: The roof is the main part of the houses that is used to harness the earth's energy. Rice and millet grown on the rooftop provide food while vegetables are grown in pots. It is a Normal roof that are precast from arch panels. Our roofs are precast arch panels. The roof has got a Cement finishing and has got a slight slope for water seepage.

Chapter 3

3 Research methodology

- Assessing the existing situation of built environment for urban agriculture.
- Interviewing with different stakeholders (university professors, agricultural professionals, students and designers) who are engaged in researching, creating awareness and capacity building on the issue of urban agriculture, which is vertical farming agriculture like aquaponics.
- Understanding the need of urban population related to urban food problems and insecurity to urban agriculture, understanding peoples know how about the idea of vertical farming and what

educational facilities do about this.

- The main theme of the project is to come up with exemplary design solution, which direct contact on the problems that are on the problem statement and go on the success to full fill the researcher's objective.

3.1 Data collection method

In this research, both primary and secondary data were collected. The secondary data for this case study has been collected from the magazines, research documents, Internet, articles, books and documentation from the case area. These secondary data were used to get a good understanding of both the research problem and the case area. Qualitative verbal analysis is will be used to gain better understanding of the research problem. Therefore, the primary data for this research are collected through personal interviews with the selected people from different parts and observation on the study Area. All the information gathered from the primary and secondary data was used to give an answer to the main research problem.

3.1.1 Primary data gathering methods

Surveys for primary data are conducted to get hold of relevant data for reliable and up-to-date information. The survey conducted includes on-site observations in the major areas of consideration, and image interpretation.

3.1.2 Observation

Collecting relevant data for analyzing the current practice of urban agriculture in the case area of Wolayita Sodo requires using or applying different methodologies. One of the best ways of obtaining a data on how urban spaces operate or used is by making site visits to the areas and observe what really is going on there i.e. through observing the relationships between activities and spaces. Observation in residential and apartment of urban agriculture takes place repetitively, and pictures of each urban agriculture practices are taken.

Observation have different purposes;

- To understand how urban agriculture relate with urban sustainability indicators.
- To identify the gap between the well-designed urban agriculture to traditional practice.

Image interpretation: - Visual interpretations were performed on the main base data of the research. The purpose of performing visual image interpretation in the process of data capturing is to support the analysis. As described above primary data is collected through two

methods, field observation and image interpretation. The following table shows the data types and description in relation with methods for data capturing of study area.

Table 1 data types

Methods	Data type	Description
Field observation	Spatial	To understand and describe the character of the newly built area in relation with urban sustainability indicators. To identify the gap between the plan and implementation of the project area.
Image interpretation	Spatial data	Identified the different land uses in the study area before and after the implementation of the project.

3.1.3 Interview

For this research, interviews were used to gather information that adds for the physical observation. The interview helps to measure the attitudes, perceptions and motivation of urban households; condominium households about urban agriculture, vertical farming. The type of questions that was asked in the interview falls into Use and Attitudes, opinions, and problems regarding urban agriculture.

In this regard a total of 40 interviews were conducted using semi- structured interview questions

3.2 Case study selection criteria

In the selection of case studies is as the researcher’s specific theme of the research revolves on the process, construction system and the idea how vertical farming be designed.

The researcher took local case study in the city of wolaita sodo, which is horizontal urban garden architecture is an input to improve vertical farming architecture.

Table 2 data source

No.	Source of the data	Data collection method	Interpretation method
	Primary data		
1	Professionals/peoples	● Interview	By taking a note

	Observation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Photographs • Pictures 	Sketch Short note
	Secondary data		

3.3 Purpose of Data Collection

The purpose of data collection is mainly to understand the feelings and experience of the society on the urban agriculture and focused on the following key issues:

#urban agriculture activities carried on the area.

#urban agriculture accessibility to the community.

Society experience on urban agriculture.

#what they feel about it

Chapter four

4.0 CONTEXTUAL BACKGROUND

Introduction

Figure 3-1: Existing boundary of the town and road network

Population size of the City

According to the data from the city finance economic development office, recently the total number of the city residents exceeds 138,253. However, the office says that the number of population is increasing

in high level due to continue rural urban migration. To this end the annual growth rate of the city population is 4.8%.

Those demographic processes are complex phenomena that are affected by social, cultural, political and physiological factors. Accordingly, in Soddo city administration immigration is too increasing from time to time.

Up to the end of 2007 E.C. Soddo city administration has a total population is 138,353.

Table 3 population size of wolaita sodo

Male	Female	Total
72,802	65,451	138,253

The use of this population analysis to the researcher

The population analysis helps to know population density and how urban farming practice include all urban households. Some urban households doesn't match practice It.; in the back yard of their residence and on the researchers population study, the population increasing dramatically time to time. So, there is also need of condominium and apartment facilities for them. The analysis helps researcher to assess the agricultural needs of this condominium and apartments.

Economic activities

The city is located in the strategic place for the southern Ethiopia at the center and it has seven outlets which are connected the north, south, east and west directions.

Economic Sectors

The city economy is primarily based on Trade and other businesses, Majority of the people are engaged on trade where as some of them are working in government and non-government organizations. In addition micro and small scale enterprise is the main source of income for many dwellers.

Function of the economic activity for the researcher

The aim of this economic activity analysis is to give consideration for all economic groups; low, medium and high class economic society. And also to answer the question how match the society can afford the project that the researcher do.

Infrastructure

Figure 4-2: Existing infrastructure of the town road

. Sodo has 27 km concrete asphalt road, 4.6 km graveled road, 53 km cobblestone road and 110 km cleaned road. There are about 10 transport institutions that organize the transport arrangement in to different routes away from Sodo city and transit transport vehicles through 7 outlets.

The function of infrastructure study to researcher

The researcher do infrastructure analysis to show how the case area infrastructure; road, water, and other different infrastructure is accessible to the community.

Climate

Climate is one of the prominent factors that affect the socio economic activities, directly or indirectly, the elements of climate include temperature, Humidity, Rain fall and Wind. All this elements affect the activity of every group of the society, including the urban community. The climate condition of Sodo city is likely to be moderate (woinadega). The average annual temperature of the town is exceeds up to 18 °C in summer season, the residents can enjoy. Fascinating sun shine for about 9 hours per day. Since the city is founded under the foot of mount damota, the weather condition becomes cool at night. This makes the city more attractive than from the surrounding. Soddy gains the rain twice a year.

Rain fall

Table 4rain fall

Station Name	Region	Zone	Wereda	Longtude	Latitude	Altitude	Year	Annual Total Rainfall in mm
Wolaitasodo	SNNPR	Wolaita	Sodo Zuria	037 ⁰ 44' 56.2" E	06 ⁰ 49' 17.6" N	1854	2018	1547.7

Temperature

Table 5 temprature

Station Name	Region	Zone	Wereda	Longtude	Latitude	Altitude	Element (Monthly)	Year
--------------	--------	------	--------	----------	----------	----------	-------------------	------

							Avg Temp in °C)	Min
Wolaitasodo	SNNPR	Wolaita	Sodo Zuria	<i>037⁰ 44'</i> <i>56.2" E</i>	<i>06⁰ 49'</i> <i>17.6"</i> <i>N</i>	<i>1854</i>	<i>Monthly Avg. Min.Temp</i>	2018

The function of this climate analysis to the researcher

The aim of this study is to understand what type of agricultural practice/ horizontal and vertical farming /; out puts/ crops, vegetables and fruits were growing in this climate. And also to study the climate influence on the farming activity and how to control it.

4.1 Case area analysis

Case Area Analysis

Aroge Arada condominium
Location: near st. Giyorgis Church
Location and background; This case area is selected by the researcher to analyze it related to urban agriculture; vertical farming on the area and to study the connection between urban agriculture and residential, apartments; condominium in case of wolaita sodo.
Location; aroge arada near st. giorgis orth. church,
Site features; the site of urban residence; apartment, condominium and the site of urban agriculture is grouped in zoning. There are condominium households, shops, and other infrastructure. Some condominium block households doesn't match practice horizontal and vertical farming like residential households.

Wadu condominium
Location and background; This case area is selected by the researcher to analyze it related to urban agriculture; vertical farming on the area and to study the connection between urban agriculture and residential, apartments; condominium in case of wolaita sodo.
Location; wadu, infront of st. Kuskuwam orth. church.
Site features; the site of urban residence; apartment, condominium and the site of urban agriculture is grouped in zoning. There are condominium households, shops, and other infrastructure. Some condominium block households doesn't match practice horizontal and vertical farming like residential households.

condominium in front of the universty
Location and background; This case area is selected by the researcher to analyze it related to urban agriculture; vertical farming on the area and to study the connection between urban agriculture and residential, apartments; condominium in case of wolaita sodo.
Location; infront of wolaita sodo university
Site features; the site of urban residence ; apartment, condominium and the site of urban agriculture is grouped in zoning. There are condominium households, shops, and other infrastructure. Some condominium block households doesn't match practice horizontal and vertical farming like residential households.

4.1.2 Context

Wolaita sodo is the most rapidly developing city in southern nation, nationalities and peoples of Ethiopia. Different business and investments are constructing. The city also known by urban horizontal agriculture; urban households practice it on backyards of their residence and some households practicing it on the balcony of the condominium within the growing pot. the figure below represents the urban agriculture activities inside the city.

Case area

It is an area selected by the researcher based on the context look out under the scope, objective, problem, and title of the researcher. So, the researcher selected three condominium sites practicing urban agriculture, vertical farming and urban agricultural landscape/ garden. These three sites are: - condominium site in front of wolaita Sodo University, condominium area in front of kuskuwam Mariam and aroge arada near St. George church.

Note: the researcher selected three sites to do case area analysis on urban agriculture; vertical farming. But there is similar urban agriculture activities; the researcher selected one of the three sites that include all activities on the rest two case areas.

So, the researcher select the condominium located in front of wolaita Sodo University. The researcher do deep context analysis on this area. Each and every detail analysis on the types of urban farming/ horizontal, vertical and mixed farming / practice on the area.

Case area: - condominium site in front of wolaita Sodo university

Figure 4-3: selected case area in front of WSU

4.1.3 Horizontal farming

Most wolaita Sodo urban households practiced horizontal urban agriculture; urban vegetable garden and fruit farming on the back yards of their house. They used it as input for food security and as an income source. On the environment households participate this farming activity as an alternative income source. Cabbage, boye (local food), boyina, lattice... Are the urban vegetable garden products and sugar cane, mango, avocado and banana are fruit products on the context.

Figure 4-4 horizontal farming practicing on the case area

This kind of farming activity trying to practice with the society as an alternative income source and food security, but it is difficult to say like this because it is not active and improved due to the following factors; like insufficient water for this purpose, lack of skilled man power to the area and lack of preserved space for this activity. And it also practicing traditional and poor farming system.

General image and site features

- The site of horizontal farming were not well integrated with residential units of the city.
- Space of farming unit is not well designed there is water management problem; surface run off of water is a critical issue.
- Circulation with in with in the farming is traditional/ informal circulation system.
- It is not designed for multi-purpose like landscape garden and food purpose, economical etc...
- It have not additional purposes for the community like; landscape, recreational area and communal space.
- It doesn't define sustainability aspects of the area from different angles.

Sustainability aspects

Sustainability aspects of horizontal farming to the case area; urban agriculture horizontal farming of the case area doesn't promote social, economic and environmental aspects of sustainability.

Social; horizontal farming practicing on the case area doesn't provide different functions like, as an recreational area, communal space, meeting together, creating social interaction and related significance. Environmental; horizontal farming of the case area is not a key solution for the problem organic waste management system in the city. Economical; we can use urban agriculture as an income source but when the researcher observes the existing horizontal farming doesn't create income.

4.1.3 Vertical farming

Figure 4-1 vertical farming garden practice on the terrace of the condominium

Vertical farming is the process of growing plants and any other farming activities in side buildings vertically or on the farming space of buildings. In the context of wolaita there is no any kind of well-designed vertical farming architecture but some condominium households growing different types of vegetables, gardens, and crops on terraces, balconies and stair landing of their condominium building; this kind of agricultural practices also categorized under vertical farming. So, vertical farming practicing by condominium households in front of wolaita sodo university and in front of kuskuwam Mariam church.

This type of farming system mostly practicing on this environment as re creational space that means to create good view on their house and related to that they use it as alternative food

source.

But the fact is to use it as an income source and food source. These problem happened lack of awareness and when the buildings designed there were no consideration of any space about this kind of farming activity.

General imaging and site features

This type of farming practice is applying on the balconies and stair landing of the condominium building.

The farming activity is poor kind of farming activity; water drainage and supply problem, the soil and water creates a mud on the balconies of the building.

Working space

There is no any kind of any designed space on the buildings; condominiums for farming activity; that means there is no any design consideration to apply vertical farming in the design process of this the context of wolaita sodo, Ethiopia.

Construction material

The vertical farming activity practiced in side of thrown pots by filling soil in to it and applying farm on it.

Aqua farm

It is a kind urban farming activity that urban dwellers practicing fish farming activity as a profession inside; urban marine, vertically integrated with hydroponics and horizontally in farming pool. These farming activities is more important areas which are lack of any water bodies near to the city; so in case of wolaita sodo it is more important to address fresh fishes to urban dwellers. Based on my analysis and data collection process there is no aqua farm in the city.

Organic waste

On the case area there is also the existence different organic wastes. Those wastes are accumulated with different areas; i.e. on the landing of stairs of the condominium blocks, on the terrace of the blocks, on the balcony and on the ground surrounding of the blocks.

Waste water

On the case area there is the existence of waste water/ gray water from toilets, bath rooms and kitchens; so there is need of waste water/ gray water treatment areas.

4.2 Data analysis

In the topic the researcher presents the analysis data from questioner, interview, focus group discussion and field observation. The analysis is focused on the problem statement and research questions within thematic and spatial scope of the research explained on chapter one.

Questionnaire

Data from agricultural experts, urban households/ community/ questionnaire were analyzed descriptive statically methods involving percentage. The responses to the questions are categorized in to two; those are responses from agricultural experts/ government officers / and respondent/ urban households responses in each category was determined.

The questions presented to the respondents in opened way and provided to all urban respondents.

the survey was applied in May 25, 2019 G.C in wolaita sodo.

Conversant agreement

This is the agreement that the researcher and the respondents discussed. Before conducting any respondents; interview or informal conversation that the researcher explained to the respondents about what the research concerned and asked for their permission for discussion and audio record.

Community survey result

This community survey was applied on the respondents in May, 2019 G.C on 40 community members. In this survey type each questions of the survey is analyzed separately and the result are discussed to gain what the community needs, attitudes, and ideas to wards science and technology. The respondents are in different part of professions and life style with age variation.

Note: the researcher prepared and presented to the respondents around 20 detail questions; from those questions the researcher do its survey result by generalizing those 20 questions to 7 generalized survey results.

Question 1. Do you have your own urban farm? A) Yes B) No, if your answer is yes when did you start to participate on urban agriculture? In years_____.

This questions investigate the community have their own urban farming or not and to know their experience in in the farming practice. The participants allowed to tick more than one options; the total percentage is 100%. Almost half of the participants/ 50%/ of the community indicate that they have their own horizontal and vertical farming and they have experience on it; about 45% of the respondents have no any farming area and 5% of the respondents are not sure on the idea.

Figure 4-2 the graph representing that the respondents practicing urban agriculture or not

Question 2. Do you know about vertical farming? A) Yes B) No; and what kind of vertical farming do you know? _____ If your answer is yes do you farm vertically? A) Yes B) No

In this question almost around 10% of the respondents know about vertical farming that is about roof garden and vegetable garden with in growing pot on their balcony of their condominium house but they have no any skill about the other types of vertical farming. Again around 70% of the respondents didn't know about vertical farming and about 20% of the respondents are not sure about it.

2. Do you know about vertical farming? if your answer is yes, do you farm vertically?

Figure 4-3 the graph representing knowhow about vertical farming

Question 3. What type of urban farming; vertical farming do you adopt?

- A) Crop B) livestock C) mixed farm D) vegetables and fruits

Where you grow it?

- A) Back yard B) open space C) inside ware house D) on growing shelf E) growing pot F) road side

This question have an aim the type of farming activity that the respondents adopt and where they practiced it.

3. what type of urban farm do you adopt? and where you grow it?

Figure 4-4 graph representing type of urban farm u adopt

Question 4. Is there any preserved any kind of vertical farming space for condominium dwellers? A) Yes B) No

If your answer is no, do you want to have? A) Yes B) No

The aim of this question is to know what the condominium house holders need related to the urban farming and to use their opinion, idea need related to vertical farming on their condominium house. Almost 100% of the respondents says that there is no any preserved space for any kinds of farming activity and almost 95 % of them wants to have designed farming space on the condominium as one infrastructure and 5% of the respondents not sure about it.

4. Is there any preserved urban farming area for condominium households? if your answer is No, do you want to have?

Figure 4-5 about space for urban agriculture on the condominium building

Question 5. Do you think urban agriculture; vertical farming has bright opportunity?

A) Yes B) No

If your answer is Yes/No bright opportunity please mention?

This question were the target question on the bright opportunities of urban agriculture; vertical farming to understand by what means the community understood urban agriculture as a bright opportunity in the life of respondents and sustainability issues. Based on these idea around 80% of the respondents participated on my questionnaire says that urban agriculture has bright opportunity; but 10% of the respondents says that it has no bright opportunity on the current situation. If it will practiced in modern way may have bright opportunity. And 10% of the respondents said that we haven't any information about it.

5.Do you think urban agriculture; vertical farming has bright opportunity ?

Figure 4-6 shows about urban agriculture and its bright future

#if your answer is Yes/No bright opportunity please mention.

This question aimed to know the opinion, idea of the respondents, why they say yes/ No.

One community member said that:-

“My name is Yonas Wubshet; I live in the city for 15 years, I have M.Sc. within pharmacy and I stay with this profession. I believed that urban agriculture has bright opportunity. That means it is one means to express sustainability issue; urban agriculture plays a role on the 3 pillars of sustainability; socially as a one source for food security, economically as an income source and environmentally by using organic wastes to get nutrients for the farming activity.”

The other community member say that:

“My Name is Matheos Kussa, I lived for 10 years in this city with trading profession. In my opinion urban agriculture has no bright opportunity because it is not sustainable on the current situation for the future it may be”

Question 6. What are the most practice of urban agriculture; vertical farming on the area?

Almost 90% of the respondents' answers by saying fruit and vegetable, 5% of the respondents says that crops and 5% of them have no idea about it.

6.what are the most practice of urban agriculture/ farming on the area?

Figure 4-7 the most practicing urban agriculture

Interview

It is a method that answers the questions by face to face interviewing.

How much organic wastes are collected from each condominium blocks? This is my interview question to both urban planning and housing office officer in Addis Ababa and wolaita sodo.

Ato. Gizachew Wakitola is officer in Addis Ababa urban planning and housing office. He answers the questions by saying “there is some statically arranged data represented there is around one plastic bag organic wastes collected from one condominium household and 1 sack of organic waste from individual block of Bulbula condominium” but there is no any related information that answers this questions but un officially Ato. Feleke says that the waste from condominium users is similar with Addis Ababa because condominium households live most probably within the same life style in Ethiopia so the data may be related.

Chapter 5

5.1 Finding, Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1.1 Finding

This area of the research comprises the main findings and conclusions of the data analyzed through the previous chapter of the research paper. The findings contain the social, environmental and economic aspects of urban agriculture; vertical farming through creating

connection between urban farming activities and housing service/ condominium house in wolaita sodo.

Major findings

- Lack of any designed space to practice vertical farming; roof garden farming, terrace garden farming, mixed agricultural and residential farming.
- Absence of knowledge about urban agriculture; vertical farming.
- There is also absence of organic waste reuse/ system design.
- Lack of infrastructure
- The orientation and form of buildings are difficult to farm in it related to sun direction.
- Requirement of large area in the existing traditional farming.
- There is a great surface runoff of water in the traditional farming.

5.1.2 Conclusion

Urban agriculture; vertical farming spaces are very important elements to urban households of the city. It plays a great role in economic, social and environmental aspects of sustainability.

Wolaita sodo is an important city in the country to have a proper urban agriculture; vertical farming residence/ apartment practice which makes it an exemplary urban agricultural city of the continent. We need to have well designed urban agriculture; vertical farming space on our condominiums or apartments as we are urban households of the city in our context. To achieve our need related to this; the first step should be understanding of the trend of urban agriculture usage / practice in the context of wolaita sodo.

The objective of this paper is to improve the concept of urban agriculture through vertical farming residential units/ apartments as a means of providing food source by creating a bond between urban households and agriculture.

5.1.3 Recommendations

For the study that the existing urban agriculture; vertical farming practicing community/ users /; the researcher recommended with different aspects of the study.

For urban households; apartment households

Social aspect

Urban agriculture should be build a bond between urban community; better interaction between peoples from different walks of life; from farmer, citizen, urban planners, NGOs and others; it should also use as a meeting space or communal and recreational space when we use it as urban landscape in horizontal farming and it also used as a recreational area by giving well designed space on apartments and using it as a seat out when it designed integrated with our apartment room.

Environmental aspect

Agricultural greenery has a great ability to release O_2 and use CO_2 . So the researcher recommended that practicing vertical farming decreases the emission of CO_2 from condominium households.

- 40cm thick plant bed/ growing rack is equivalent use as an insulation layer which reduces heat gain to a great extent. And also it helps reduction of indoor temperature, improve air quality and surface run off/ in farm land /.
- Methods of grey water reuse for plant reduce environmental waste by using toilet wastes and other organic wastes as extra fertilizer for the plants.

Economic aspect

The researcher recommended urban agriculture; vertical farming as economic aspects for urban households as income source. And it also reduces the cost for food and other related costs like transportation cost for food delivery. Urban households also used as one means of creating job opportunity.

Architectural aspect

The researcher recommend that vertical farming apartments are a tool in solving problems related to green building, energy, aesthetic, technology and related problems for architects. So architects should practice it in any kind of designs. As farming architecture is the bridge that connects architecture and agriculture so vertical farming apartments play a major role.

Political aspect

Currently our country is in political chaos and Ethiopian community raising different questions related with social, economic, environmental and political so architects have a great role in solving related problems vertical farming apartment also have role in solving social and economic and environmental problems as I told on the above discussions.

Recommendations in different level

Town and city level

The researcher recommended to landscape architect, urban planner, urban farmer and community director needs to work in collaborate to support, design and guide to urban farming. And to use urban farming as available public, private and community space for recreational and growing food purpose.

Apartments/ residential levels

The researcher recommend urban households to use urban agriculture; vertical farming in their residential and apartment buildings by considering design guidelines. Using back yards of residential building and creating a back yard space in apartment building.

For government

In fact most peoples of the city still have low income; however most respondents talked that some communities practicing farming activity. There for the government should give awareness with related professionals of urban agriculture expert and architects.

Note: - the recent urban zoning of the city grouped/ provide urban agriculture zone outside the city. The researcher recommend to urban planners of the city should provide agricultural zone at the center of the city and integrate it within residential urban zone not only outside of the city.

General recommendation

- Provide well designed farming space to urban /apartment households.
- Creating bond between agriculture and urban households.
- Creating a back yard feeling on apartment house holds.
- Creating apartment scape; recreational and communal seat out on apartments.
- Crating linkage between urban households and farming environment.
- Design waste water management/ water treatment units that solve the problem of infrastructure.

- Create a method of re using organic wastes from the apartment users by using organic waste management system/ compost design.
- Giving awareness to the community.

Chapter 6

6.1 Design proposal

6.1.1 Site selection criteria

Location

In urban context urban households are mostly around apartment areas and residential areas. The facility of urban agriculture; vertical farming should be in the area residential development and apartment areas of the city and this creates good opportunity to the households of the city and government to practice urban agriculture in the backyards residences; apartment buildings and to give health, food security respectively.

Zoning

The site only nearby the site from the case/ condominium in front of wolaita Sodo University/ of the thesis and allowable by the structural map of wolaita sodo city qualified for residential and apartment.

Neighborhood

The site near to the public facilities such as educational institutions/ wolaita sodo university /, residential/ condominium and residence /, super markets, bank services and commercial areas.

Transportation

In front of the site there is a high way from wolaita sodo to Arbaminch which creates a good opportunity for urban households nearby.

Strength of the site

- It is easily accessible from Main Street and pedestrian near the site.
- There educational institutions/ wolaita sodo university/, liqa school, residential; condominium and service area around the site and also many visitors have a chance to

visit this vertical farming apartment and it creates a chance for educational visits.

- It has good air circulation because there is also Damota mountain nearby and Lake Abaya which creates the area more comfortable atmosphere.

- It has minimum degree slope.

Figure 6-1 location map

Vegetation

Figure 6-2 vegetation and utility

Circulation/ road analysis

Figure 6-3 road analysis

Neighborhood/ surrounding analysis and climate analysis

Figure 6-4 zoning and climate analysis

Site area and site section

Figure 6-5 site area and site section

Design Concept and development

Design concept

My design concept divides the site in to two main zones; agricultural production zone and residential zone. Further more water management integrated in to both zones to limit water conception, demonstrate agricultural/ green infrastructure practice.

The production zone consists an integrated system of growing beds, aqua tanks/fish farm tank/, and garden agriculture integrated with apartment households of apartments as a backyard sense.

Orientation and inclination farm of the building are integrated with the sun direction.

My design also have a compost area/ organic waste as natural fertilizer/ and water treatment zone.

Program development

Vertical farming Apartment

3 bed		Size/ area/	Quantity /No/
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vertical farming/back yard Vertical farming Store Kitchen Dining area 	5m*3m=15m ² 3m* 2m=6 m ² 4m* 3m=12m ² 3m* 3m=9m ² 5m*3m =15m ²	5

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Living area • Rest room • Agricultural garden area • Master bed • Bed /2/ 	$2m * 2m = 4m^2$ $3m * 2m = 6m^2$ $3m * 5m = 15m^2$ $2m * 4m = 8m^2$	
2 bed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical farming/back yard farming • Store • Kitchen • Dining area • Living area • Rest room • Agricultural garden area • Master bed • Bed /1 	$4m * 3m = 12m^2$ $3m * 2m = 6m^2$ $3m * 3m = 9m^2$ $3m * 2m = 6m^2$ $4m * 3m = 12m^2$ $3m * 1m = 3m^2$ $2m * 2m = 4m^2$ $3m * 4m = 12m^2$ $2m * 3m = 6m^2$	8
1 bed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vertical farming/back yard farming • Kitchen • Living area • Rest room • Agricultural garden area • Master bed 	$3m * 3m = 9m^2$ $4m * 2m = 8m^2$ $3m * 3m = 9m^2$ $2m * 2m = 4m^2$ $2m * 2m = 4m^2$ $3m * 3m = 9m^2$	10
Restaurant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kitchen • Store • Dinning 	$6m * 5m = 30m^2$ $3m * 3m = 9m^2$ $10m * 8m = 80m^2$	1
Show room		$50m^2$	1
Germination area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Seed germination • Germination bed 	$10m * 4m = 40m^2$ $8m * 2m = 16m^2$	1

Waste recycling area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water recycling unit • Organic waste recycling unit • Toilet waste recycling area 	$8m*5m = 40m^2$ $8m*5m = 40m^2$ $5m*8m = 40m^2$	1
Parking area		$20m*6m + 100m = 220m^2$	
Horizontal / agricultural landscape		-----	4
Market area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supermarket • Shops • Traditional market area 	$8m*5m = 40m^2$ $10m*3m = 30m^2$ $10m*8m = 80m^2$	1

Site plan

Floor plan

Ground floor

First floor

2nd floor

3rd floor

4th floor

5th floor

6th floor

7th floor

8th floor

9th floor

10th floor

Section

Elevations

Front elevation

Rare

elevation

Right side elevation

Left

side

elevation

Detail

3D

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- 31 Structural map of wolaita sodo
- 32 South region or SNNAP profile

Appendix

QUESTIONNAIRES

Part I: Household Background Information

Wolaita sodo, _____, Household ID-----Date & Month-----Enumerator-

a. Questions Related to Household Characteristics:

1. Now the researcher starts asking you some questions about you and the members of your family. Please take time to answer about other members of your family.

Full Name	Relation to Primary	Year born	Gender	Education level (yrs) Education
-----------	---------------------	-----------	--------	---------------------------------

	Respondent			level (yrs)

2. What is the marital status of the primary respondent? 1) Single 2) Married 3) Divorced 4) Separated

1) What type of house do you live? 1) Own House 2) Private rented 3) Kebele rented 4) condominium house/apartment

B Socio-Economic Characteristics of the Households:

1. What is the on-farm income of the household? _____

2. What is the off-farm income of the household? _____

3. Could you tell us something about your expenditure? _____ Now we will

4. Did you get any remittance from abroad/NGO? 1) Yes 0) No

If yes, in kind/cash, how much? _____

5. What is the farm size of the household in hectare (ha)? -----

Urban Agriculture:- vertical farming related characteristics

Table 6 questionnaire

S n	List of attitudinal measurements	Is this a benefit?	Please rank the benefits as per the following scale					
		Yes or No	Very Import	Important	Undecided	Less import	Not import	Total
1	Create income source							
2	Contribute to food security							
3	Solve waste water and organic waste problems in to a productive resource							

4	Educational value							
5	Reduce household expense							
6	Recreational opportunities for citizens							
7	creating land marks							
8	Sustainability							

1. Do you have your own a farm (do you participate in urban agriculture)? 1) Yes 0) No
2. Do you know about vertical farming? 1) Yes 0) No
3. When did you start to participate on urban agriculture? (in yrs) -----
4. Do you have access to credit? 1) Yes 0) No
5. Do you have extension contact? 1) Yes 0) No
If yes how often 1) Daily 2) weakly 3) Monthly 4) Bi-Monthly

6 What type of urban farming, vertical farming do you adopt? 1) Crop only 2) Livestock only
3) Mixed farming 4) fruit 5) vegetables

7. Where do you grow crops and rear animals?

- 1) In backyards 2) In open space 3) In ware house 4) on growing shelf 5) in high rise building
- 6) In urban fringe areas 7) Road side/others

8. Do you apply improved seed? 1) Yes 0) No

9. Do you use improved cows? 1) Yes 0) No

10. Could you tell me some information about your farming activities?

11. Do you get any professionals training about urban agriculture, vertical farming? 1) Yes 0) No

12. Do you want to have back yard in your condominium houses? 1) Yes 0) no

13. Are you farming vertically? 1) Yes 0) no

If your answer is no, why you don't farm vertically?

1) Lack of knowledge 2) I think that is difficult 3) any other _____

—

If your answer is yes, when do you start it (in yrs)_____.

14. Is there any farming area for condominium dwellers? 1) Yes 2) no

If your answers no, do you want to have? 1) Yes 2) No

C. respondents view

1. Do you think working on urban agriculture, vertical farming has bright future? 1) Yes 0) No

2. If, yes / no bright opportunity, please mention some of them.

Working in urban agriculture

1. What are the most important practices of urban farming in the area?

2. Do you face any challenges while farming? If yes, can you mention them starting with the most important. _____

-

3. How you are tackling these problems? _____

4. What are the opportunities engaging in vertical farming in production, marketing and financial aspect? _____

5. How do you evaluate the sustainability of urban agriculture? _____

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Thanks for answering this question

